

TAKING STOCK OF THE WAR IN UKRAINE: IMPLICATIONS FOR GERMANY AND THE EU.

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POLICY STATEMENT

The 'special military operation' launched by Moscow against Ukraine surprised European decision-makers, despite all warnings and military mobilization since 2021, thus destabilizing the region and the global economy. The military offensive received harsh responses from Western peers, as broad military support for Kyiv and severe economic sanctions were put in place. However, despite the efforts to stop the war, Europe's dependence on cheap Russian energy resources (mainly gas) remains, posing a double challenge: to maintain security stability in European territory and at the same time seek an alternative energy source that, in the short term, meets growing consumer demands. This Policy Brief aims to evaluate the reflexes of the Russian military onslaught against Ukraine and its implications for the EU and its geoeconomic powerhouse, Germany.

BACKGROUND

On February 24, 2022, Russia launched a large-scale military attack – aerial strikes, artillery attacks, and the sending of troops on three different fronts – against Ukraine. Among the declared objectives that permeate this "special military operation", as Moscow so called it, are (I) the neutralization of Ukraine; (II) the recognition of Crimea as a Russian territory; (III) the recognition of the independence of the Donbas republics, and (IV) the 'denazification' of Ukraine.

In addition to immediate formal condemnations, the primary response of Western powers – led by the US, the UK, and the EU – was the imposition of drastic sanctions on Russia to mitigate its ability to finance the war effort. Chiefly among them is a series of embargoes aimed at the backbone of the Russian economy and natural resources, added to a ban from the SWIFT payments system, as well as individual sanctions against business magnates and influential political figures of President Vladimir Putin's inner circle.

After six months of conflict, the redirection of forces now concentrates the clashes in the southern and eastern portions of the Ukrainian territory. This process is marked by strenuous offensive and counter-offensive operations of urban warfare, which prolong the conflict, the economic sanctions attached, and their reflexes on the EU and, especially, Germany.

FINDINGS

On the eve of the outbreak of the conflict, the message coming from Berlin was clear: Germany would not consent to an attack on Ukrainian sovereignty. Thus, it was willing to bear the costs of breaking a position of pragmatic neutrality to protect European fundamental rights and values.

On the one hand, this is a clear manifestation of the historical transition from a realist pre-World Wars great power to a civilian power that, unlike the former, aims to 'civilize' international relations by strengthening international norms and rules. Conversely, it comes with a paradox, as the conflict on European territory also served as a turning point for Europe's security arrangement and German defense policy.

German national effort to preserve the political and security order in Europe comprises the creation of a €100 billion (US\$113 billion) military fund and a NATO-standard commitment of 2% of GDP to defense spending, as announced by chancellor Olaf Scholz. In addition, there is the sending of 1,000 anti-tank systems and 500 Stinger anti-aircraft weapons to the Ukrainian military, reversing both the principle of not sending weapons to crisis zones and the civilian character of a post-war defense policy that accepted firm limits on its armed forces.

The USA captains the resistance of Ukrainian forces. The American government's commitment to the conflict reached US\$54 billion – the sum of the two emergency aid packages approved by Congress in March (US\$13.6bn) and May (US\$40bn). In comparison, the EU has so far announced a diminished sum of €2.5bn in funding to Ukraine through the European Peace Facility (EPF) but offers crucial logistic support for the equipment that arrives from the other side of the Atlantic. In addition to the humanitarian nature of both aid packages, the bulk of their financial support is earmarked for intelligence and counter-intelligence, as well as military supplies and weapons (N.d, 2022a; 2022b)ⁱⁱⁱ.

Furthermore, Germany's commitment to NATO was expanded, including increasing its deterrence presence in Lithuania and making air defense systems available to NATO member countries in Eastern Europe. German chancellor Olaf Scholz also reiterated the country's central role as a NATO member and indicated a possible shift in the acquisition of F/A-18 Super Hornets by state-of-the-art F-35 fighter aircraft capable of carrying nuclear weapons to replace its Tornado bombers.

However, how does this impact the region's security dynamic? It is essential to underline that, in addition to the declared objectives of Moscow regarding the invasion of Ukraine, there are also motivations of strategic nature. NATO's enlargement towards its borders is attributable to the advancement of its military infrastructure and ballistic missile defense systems. This impairs the logic of mutually assured destruction (MAD), which governs the precepts of deterrence between nuclear powers, exposing Russian nuclear forces to a first attack with diminished responsiveness. In the eyes of the Kremlin, this change would intensify competition for securitization in Europe, triggering a new escalation in the disposition of weapons systems in strategic regions for their defense, such as Kaliningrad and Crimea.

Moreover, Berlin complied with the economic sanctions imposed on Moscow, putting the Nord Stream 2 gas pipeline on standby, a joint energy project in the Baltic Sea that complements the preexisting Nord Stream 1 pipeline. Nord Stream 1 departs from Vyborg in northwestern Russia near the Finnish border and Nord Stream 2 from Ust-Luga near the Estonian border. Both flow into the northeast region of Germany through the state of Mecklenburg-Vorpommern. Each system comprises a twin pipeline with a flow capacity of up to 27.5 billion cubic meters of gas per year, potentially reaching up to 155 billion cubic meters combined if both pipeline systems (Nord Stream 1 and 2) are fully operational.

Over the last ten years, German dependence on the Russian energy market has increased significantly, the largest in the EU. Consumption of Russian natural gas in Germany has increased from 40% territory to 55%, and the same pattern is observed regarding Russian oil, which increased from 38% to 42%. In 2021, trade between Russia and Germany reached 59.8 billion, with a deficit for Berlin – €33.1 billion against 26.6 billion euros. In May 2022, Germany recorded its first monthly trade deficit since 1991. Crude oil and natural gas imports from Russia amounted to €19.4 billion – an increase of around 49.5% compared to the previous year (N.d, 2022c)^{iv}.

However, dependence on the Russian energy market is not exclusive to Berlin. The EU has Russia as its leading supplier of energy resources: oil (29%), natural gas (43%), and solid fossil fuels such as coal (54%) (N.d, 2020d)^v. For this reason, significant movements toward new supply routes bypass the Russian supplier matrix and its logistics infrastructures, such as the BTC (Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan), Nabucco, and White Stream pipelines.

The war in Ukraine has further exacerbated the limits of this interdependence and the Russians' gamble on the energy market as a tool of persuasion in disputes with the West, highlighted by the indefinite shutdown of Nord Stream 1 announced by Gazprom on September 2, 2022, as a response to the economic sanctions and the suspension of the Nord Stream 2 certificate. The economic warfare has also made the Kremlin adopt measures to circumvent sanctions and negotiate with their remaining commercial partners to comply with contracts in rubles – a movement that adds to the ongoing global processes of de-dollarization of the world economy and shifting power structures.

CONCLUSIONS

The European reaction to the war in Ukraine was two-fold: it relied heavily on trade sanctions and recognized the need for increased military spending in a volatile global scenario. The latter is directly linked to a series of weapon transfers to Ukraine, which altered the war's course. Among them is Lockheed Martin's M142 HIMARS (High Mobility Artillery Rocket System), the world's most technically advanced mobile artillery system.

In 2022, Russia became the most sanctioned country in the world, surpassing Iran, and is set for the first debit default since 1998. More than a century ago, US President Woodrow Wilson hailed economic sanctions as "something more tremendous than war itself." Within hyper-globalization (1), sanctions fulfilled that realization: they became an economic weapon with more devastating potential impacts than limited and local war (2).

However, the debate on sanctions, which dates back to the 1990s, mainly points to the low effectiveness of this mechanism for resolving international conflicts (3). For example, sanctions have failed to deter Iran from enriching uranium, North Korea's leaders from its nuclear program, or the regimes of Bashar Al-Asad in Syria and Nicolás Maduro in Venezuela.

Furthermore, the imposition of trade sanctions on Russia should provide an ever-closer relationship between the Kremlin and other emerging market countries, such as the BRICS, through new infrastructure projects led by China. Moscow and New Delhi, for example, are already trading natural gas directly in rubles rather than in dollars. Furthermore, Asia already offers an alternative to SWIFT: The Cross-Border Interbank Payment System (CIPS). At the same time, they have come with an equally heavy price for Germany and other European countries, which now face a dire winter ahead as the replacement of Russia as an energy provider seems achievable only in the medium and long run.

Finally, the 'accidental revolution' in military spending in Germany and the EU, prompted by Putin (4), has the potential of fulfilling the lofty foreign policy and security ambitions of what has been called the Munich Consensus following the release of Germany's latest White Paper in 2016. The post-war civilian power has been faced once again with the perils of dismissing autonomous hard power and deterrence capabilities alongside its diplomatic principles of multilateral and peaceful insertion.

RECOMENDATIONS

(i) The EU should rethink its sanctions strategy, which had a more significant impact on some of its member-states, such as Germany – as well as the global economy in general, with particular prejudice to Global South countries – than on Russian perception and intentions toward the war.

(ii) Germany should maintain a minimum of 2% GDP defense budget to consubstantiate its global stance as a regional and economic power. By doing so, however, Berlin will have to choose between strengthening NATO and, thus, its dependence on the USA's security umbrella or prioritizing the European Defense Union (EDU) structures.

(iii) EU countries should proceed with caution regarding escalating weapon transfers to Ukrainian military forces, as this could prompt an unpredictable response from the Kremlin as the military campaign is prolonged. This movement could also lead to a reaction surpassing conventional weapons to tactical nuclear weapons.

(iv) As economic relations with Russia reach a point of no return, the EU should focus on building autonomous energetic capacities. This could be achieved by following the German example, which intends to get 100% of its energy from renewable sources by as early as 2035.

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